

Dark Matter and Relativistic Mass

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Abstract

We present a novel approach to dark matter based on relativistic mass and the perturbation parameter of negative gravity within general relativity (GR). Rather than employing the standard GR framework directly, we formulate an energetic approach for free fall applied to the universe as a whole, from which a new dimensionless parameter q is derived. This parameter represents the ratio of the relativistic mass of the universe to its rest mass at baryonic matter density, and is shown to equal both the Lorentz factor β and the ratio Ω_m/Ω_b of the matter to baryonic density parameters. From $q(a)$, the cosmic expansion velocity $v(a)$ and the Hubble parameter $H(a)$ are derived. The computed $H(a)$ shows excellent agreement with empirical data. The world radius is determined by numerical integration to $R_0 = 1.29 \times 10^{26}$ m. We argue that dark matter arises naturally from the relativistic mass contribution described by q , and that the perturbation parameter of negative gravity has been overlooked in standard cosmology.

1 Introduction

negative gravity is already part of general relativity (GR). It is referred to as the perturbation parameter because it appears so negligibly small that even A. Einstein chose not to pursue it further — though he does mention it. To the author, however, it emerges as significant in the context of his studies, which he wishes to demonstrate through this paper. His perturbation parameter does not differ from the one in GR, but is derived by a different route (see Appendix B and C), from which new possibilities arise. Moreover, anti-gravitation acquires a new dimension through the perturbation parameter by means of relativistic masses.

The author's approach has little in common with the standard framework of GR, which handles energies only with difficulty. Instead, an energetic ap-

proach for free fall is formulated for the universe, from which a new expression for the density parameter ratio is derived. This new expression, named q (see Appendix C), represents the ratio of the matter density parameter to the baryonic matter density parameter:

$$q = \beta = \frac{\Omega_m}{\Omega_b} \quad (1)$$

This yields four expressions for the ratio of relativistic mass M to rest mass M_0 : $\frac{M}{M_0}$, β , q , and $\frac{\Omega_m}{\Omega_b}$. The Lorentz factor is defined as:

$$\beta = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} \quad (2)$$

This ultimately has the advantage of allowing the true expansion velocity v of the universe to be determined, and from it the Hubble parameter $H(a)$, which can be used to assess the validity of the theory since empirical data exist for comparison.

2 Energetic Approach for Free Fall

The energy balance of the universe is obtained by substituting $M = M_0q$ and $R = a(t) R_0$ for the radius of the universe at age t , where R_0 is provisionally set to $R_0 = ct_0$. This gives the main equation:

$$M_0c^2(q-1) + M_0qc^2 = \frac{1}{2} \left(M_0c^2 - M_0q \left(c \left(1 - \frac{M_0qG}{a(t) R_0 c^2} \right) \right)^2 \right) + \frac{4}{3} \pi \rho_\Lambda R_0^3 c^2 \quad (3)$$

The terms are defined as follows:

- $M_0c^2(q-1)$: kinetic energy of the mass of the universe
- M_0qc^2 : energy of the relativistic mass of the universe
- $\frac{1}{2} \left(M_0c^2 - M_0q \left(c \left(1 - \frac{M_0qG}{a(t) R_0 c^2} \right) \right)^2 \right)$: potential energy (derivation see Appendix 1.2)
- $\frac{4}{3} \pi \rho_\Lambda R_0^3 c^2$: energy of the Big Bang (dark energy)

3 Dark Matter

From equation (3), $q(a)$ is extracted (see Appendix 2):

$$q(a) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v(a)^2}{c^2}}} \quad (4)$$

with

$$v(a) = c \sqrt{1 - \frac{1}{q(a)^2}} \quad (5)$$

The profile of q — the ratio of the relativistic mass of the universe to the rest mass at the baryonic matter density — differs markedly from that implied by the standard scale factor $a(t)$ of GR. Nevertheless, via β and q , a means to determine the expansion velocity v of the universe becomes apparent.

The modern picture of the universe — the concept of an infinitely large raisin-bread cosmos — permits a radically new perspective on the motion of galaxies, albeit perhaps more virtual than real. Specifically, an observer moves relative to the celestial bodies at the cosmic horizon. Every observer, every galaxy, is the centre of its own cosmic horizon, moving at the speed of light, or at least very nearly so, relative to all celestial bodies on that horizon (placing the centre of the horizon in the galaxy at the horizon). What is striking is that the observer — the galaxy — moves simultaneously relative to the entire moving spherical surface of the horizon. This is not to be expected of a single centre, and the author therefore describes this extraordinarily rapid motion as *virtual*.

4 Hubble Parameter

The Hubble parameter is defined via the expansion velocity as:

$$H(a) = \frac{v(a)}{a(t) R_0} \quad (6)$$

5 World Radius

The age of the universe follows readily from the scale factor a . The world radius R_0 is less straightforward and was provisionally set to $R_0 = ct_0$. From

Figure 1: The function $q(a)$ as a function of the scale factor a . This is the primary result of the model.

the energy balance and q , it emerges that q also corresponds to $\frac{\Omega_m}{\Omega_b}$. On this basis, R_0 is determined by numerical integration of the expansion velocity:

$$R_0 = \int_0^{t_0} v(t) dt \quad (7)$$

The value of $\Omega_{m,0}$ is fine-tuned until the radius obtained from this integration (R_{01}) agrees with the radius obtained from the iterative Newton procedure below. This reconciliation yields $\Omega_{m,0} = 0.31882533$.

Input: initial estimate R_0 , tolerance ε , $\Omega_{m,0}$, Ω_b

Output: converged R_0

$R_0 \leftarrow R_0 - \varepsilon \cdot 10$;

$n \leftarrow 0$;

while $n \leq 3$ **do**

compute $q(R_0) = \frac{\Omega_{m,0}}{\Omega_b}$;

// Newton step

$R_0 \leftarrow R_0 - \frac{q(R_0) - \frac{\Omega_{m,0}}{\Omega_b}}{\frac{d}{dR_0} \left(q(R_0) - \frac{\Omega_{m,0}}{\Omega_b} \right)}$;

$n \leftarrow n + 1$;

end

return R_0

Algorithm 1: Newton procedure for the world radius R_0

Figure 2: The Hubble parameter $H(a)$ computed from the model (with factor Mpc/1000).

R_0 converges to 1.29×10^{26} m, while $ct_0 = 1.301 \times 10^{26}$ m.

6 Conclusion

Kinetic energy and relativistic mass, and thus dark matter, correspond primarily with potential energy, as follows from equation (3), which is explained by the fact that dark energy is fixed. The author envisions the Big Bang similarly to a supernova, in which a large part of the originally present matter is expelled — except that this is not possible for the universe, since space and time only come into existence through it. That the energy balance (3) evaluates to zero on closer inspection is a surprise: the initial energy is apparently very small relative to the rearranged energies from which everything arises, as S. Hawking postulated with his universe from nothing.

The recognition that the standard scale factor a , as we know it, does not correlate with the expansion history described here poses significant difficulties. The perturbation parameter of antigravitation from GR is not part of the scale factor a used here. The author hopes that adding this perturbation parameter to the existing GR framework will not prove too complex, or that at least a numerical solution will be possible.

Figure 3: Empirical Hubble parameter for comparison [2]. The figure originates from a student project supervised by Prof. M. Bartelmann (Universität Heidelberg). The model (Fig. 2) shows excellent agreement.

A Parameters and Definitions

The scale factor $a(t)$ as a function of cosmic time t :

$$a(t) = \left(\sqrt{\frac{\Omega_{m,0}}{1 - \Omega_{m,0}}} \sinh\left(\frac{3 H_0 t \sqrt{1 - \Omega_{m,0}}}{2}\right) \right)^{2/3} \quad (8)$$

Present cosmic time t_0 :

$$t_0 = -\frac{2}{3} \frac{\sinh^{-1}\left(\frac{-1 + \Omega_{m,0}}{\Omega_{m,0}} \sqrt{\frac{\Omega_{m,0}}{1 - \Omega_{m,0}}}\right)}{H_0 \sqrt{1 - \Omega_{m,0}}} \quad (9)$$

Start time interval t_1 :

$$t_1 = -\frac{2}{3} \frac{\sinh^{-1}\left(a_1^{3/2} \frac{-1 + \Omega_{m,0}}{\Omega_{m,0}} \sqrt{\frac{\Omega_{m,0}}{1 - \Omega_{m,0}}}\right)}{H_0 \sqrt{1 - \Omega_{m,0}}} \quad (10)$$

Symbol	Definition
$\Omega_{m,0} = 0.3188$	matter density parameter (1.2% above literature value)
$\Omega_{\Lambda} = 1 - \Omega_{m,0}$	dark energy density parameter
$\rho_{\Lambda} = \Omega_{\Lambda} \rho_c$	dark energy density
$\Omega_b = 0.0496$	baryonic matter density parameter
$\rho_b = \Omega_b \rho_c$	baryonic matter density
G	gravitational constant
c	speed of light
$H_0 = 67.4 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$	Hubble constant [3]
$M_0 = \frac{4}{3}\pi R_0^3 \rho_b$	primary (baryonic) mass of universe
$\rho_c = \frac{3H_0^2}{8\pi G}$	critical density

Table 1: Constants and parameters used in this work.

B Derivation of Negative Gravity

This appendix presents two independent derivations of the gravitational acceleration, as developed in [1], both leading to the same result. The key insight is a relativistic correction term that modifies Newton's gravity at small distances.

Escape Velocity Approach

The starting point is the requirement that time dilation due to motion equals time dilation due to gravity (taken in absolute terms, i.e. relative to infinite distance):

$$1 - \frac{MG}{rc^2} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \quad (11)$$

This yields the escape velocity:

$$v = \sqrt{2 \frac{MG}{r} - \frac{M^2 G^2}{r^2 c^2}} \quad (12)$$

which in ordinary conditions is very close to the classical escape velocity $v_e = \sqrt{2MG/r}$ derived from energy conservation.

A second route uses the average acceleration along the path from infinity to the surface. Applying uniform-acceleration kinematics:

$$s = \frac{1}{2}at^2, \quad v = at, \quad t = \frac{v}{a} \Rightarrow s = \frac{1}{2}a\left(\frac{v}{a}\right)^2 \Rightarrow v = \sqrt{2as} \quad (13)$$

Transferring this to the escape velocity by replacing the average acceleration with an integral of the local gravitational function $f(g)$:

$$\bar{g} = \frac{\int_r^\infty f(g) dr}{s}, \quad s = \infty - r \Rightarrow v = \sqrt{2 \int_r^\infty f(g) dr} \quad (14)$$

Substituting the velocity from the time-dilation comparison:

$$2 \frac{MG}{r} - \frac{M^2 G^2}{r^2 c^2} = 2 \int_r^\infty f(g) dr \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{MG}{r} - \frac{M^2 G^2}{2r^2 c^2} = \int_r^\infty f(g) dr \quad (16)$$

Differentiating with respect to r gives the gravitational acceleration:

$$g = \frac{d}{dr} \left(\frac{MG}{r} - \frac{M^2 G^2}{2r^2 c^2} \right) = -\frac{MG}{r^2} + \frac{M^2 G^2}{r^3 c^2} \quad (17)$$

Since acceleration decreases with increasing distance (i.e. it decelerates), the sign is reversed for comparison with the surface gravitational acceleration:

$$\boxed{g = \frac{MG}{r^2} - \frac{M^2 G^2}{r^3 c^2}} \quad (18)$$

This holds under the assumption that the velocity derived from the time-dilation comparison equals the second cosmic velocity. In ordinary conditions this differs only very slightly from Newton's law of gravitation.

Speed of Light Approach

The same result is obtained by a completely independent route. By Newton's energy conservation for free fall, $E_{pot} + E_{kin} = \text{const}$, with $E_{pot} = mU$. For a particle starting from rest at R :

$$E_{kin}(r) = E_{pot}(R) - E_{pot}(r) = \Delta E_{pot} \quad (19)$$

According to Einstein, $E = mc^2$. The speed of light changes across a gravitational potential difference as:

$$c' = c \left(1 - \frac{\Delta U}{c^2} \right) \quad (20)$$

so a modified energy expression $E' = mc'^2$ can be formulated. The energy difference over the distance, using free fall ($\Delta E = E_{Start} - E_{Ziel}$), is:

$$\Delta E = m(c^2 - c'^2) \quad (21)$$

With $\Delta E_{pot} + E_{kin} = \Delta E$ and the gravitational energy taken as half of ΔE :

$$\Delta E_{pot} = \frac{1}{2} \Delta E = \frac{1}{2} \left(mc^2 - m \left(c \left(1 - \frac{MG}{rc^2} \right) \right)^2 \right) \quad (22)$$

Since $\Delta E_{pot} = m \Delta U$ and with $R = \infty$ so $U_{Start} = 0$:

$$m(-U_{Ziel}) = \frac{1}{2} \left(mc^2 - m \left(c \left(1 - \frac{MG}{rc^2} \right) \right)^2 \right) \quad (23)$$

Solving for U_{Ziel} :

$$U_{Ziel} = -\frac{1}{2} \left(c^2 - \left(c \left(1 - \frac{MG}{rc^2} \right) \right)^2 \right) \quad (24)$$

Taking $g = dU_{Ziel}/dr$ yields the same gravitational acceleration as equation (18):

$$g = \frac{d}{dr} \left[-\frac{1}{2} \left(c^2 - \left(c \left(1 - \frac{MG}{rc^2} \right) \right)^2 \right) \right] = \frac{MG}{r^2} - \frac{M^2 G^2}{r^3 c^2} \quad (25)$$

C World Radius Calculation Sheet

References

- [1] Daniel Adamczyk. Calculation of the cosmic expansion rate. Unpublished manuscript, n.d.
- [2] Matthias Bartelmann. Student project figure: empirical Hubble parameter. Unpublished student project, Universität Heidelberg, courtesy of Prof. M. Bartelmann, n.d.
- [3] Planck Collaboration. Planck 2018 results. VI. cosmological parameters. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 641:A6, 2020.

Figure 4: MathCad calculation sheet for the determination of the world radius R_0 . Two values are compared: R_0 from iteration and R_{01} from integration, reconciled manually using $\Omega_{m,0} = 0.31882533$.

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